

GOODS ACCORDING TO THE NOMENCLATURE OF GOODS EFFECT OF CLASSIFICATION ON CUSTOMS DUTIES

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Abstract: In the article, the problems arising in the process of classification of goods according to the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity are analyzed for some types of goods. Also, it is justified that the customs value of the goods and the customs rates applied to them depend on the correct classification of the goods according to the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity. In the research carried out in foreign countries and in the republic, it was found that, for example, the complete classification of foreign economic activity according to the commodity nomenclature based on the chemical composition of perfumery and cosmetic products was not provided. For this reason, the goal of our research is to classify some goods in the nomenclature of foreign economic activity based on their chemical composition, and to assign different duty rates to one group of goods (for example: 10%, 15% and 20%), the same import duty rates. determination is based on expediency. Scientific and practical proposals and recommendations have been developed to eliminate the above shortcomings.

Key words: Customs system, Central customs laboratory, customs expertise, Foreign economic activity participants, Foreign economic activity commodity nomenclature, classification, customs clearance, customs cargo declaration, commodity code, duty rate, customs value, customs fees.

Introduction.

A number of noble ideas such as ensuring the well-being of the population, creating decent living conditions for our people, and increasing the economic

potential of our country are embodied in the reforms implemented in every aspect of our life. This is reflected in changes and updates in the customs system. Large-scale works are being carried out in our country in order to expand the production capacity of industrial products and support exports, create additional jobs, and create a number of conveniences and eases for entrepreneurs.

In order to further improve the customs administration, the important attention paid to the implementation of international norms and standards into the national legislation, the systematic reforms implemented in the field serve to strengthen the country's economic stability, increase its investment potential, create a favorable business environment for the participants of foreign economic activity, and ensure the transparency of the activities of the customs authorities.

Determining whether the customs value of the goods submitted for clearance in the customs practice, the customs value of the goods, the correct calculation of the customs fees, and the correct use of the benefits provided for by the customs fees in accordance with the current legislation directly depends on the correct classification of the goods according to the nomenclature of goods of Foreign Economic Activity. Therefore, in order to avoid errors in this regard, each customs officer is required to have a perfect knowledge of the generally accepted rules for the classification of goods. Along with theoretical knowledge, it is necessary to be able to apply them directly in practice, to be constantly familiar with normative and legal documents, and to be able to widely use the latest innovative or practical methods and technical approaches in this direction.

In order to create favorable conditions for business, a number of systematic reforms are being implemented in the customs system of Uzbekistan. It should be noted that during the 2012-2017 reforms, measures were taken to improve the customs administration in the Republic. More than 20 laws and regulatory documents regulating export-import operations were adopted, which served to create favorable conditions for participants of foreign economic activity, shorten the reporting period, reduce licensed activities and other procedures.

The practice of obtaining all certificates submitted in the process of export and import of goods electronically to the automated information system "Single window" developed by the customs authorities was introduced. It is also necessary to introduce preliminary decisions on the country of origin of goods processed in the customs territory, to simplify the form of customs cargo declaration and customs value declaration.

Presidential Decree No. 5414 of April 12, 2018 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Fundamentally Improve the Activities of the State Customs Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan", Presidential Decree No. 122 of April 27, 2022 "On Additional Measures to Improve the Customs Administration" On the basis of decrees no.

In the implementation of foreign economic relations, that is, in the process of export and import of goods, each commodity is systematically classified according to international code numbers based on the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity based on the Harmonized System.

According to the main 6 rules of interpretation of foreign economic activity commodity nomenclature, goods are classified. In order to correctly determine the code of the goods, it is done by studying all their features. As mentioned above, customs fees are charged in full on the basis of determining the correct foreign economic activity commodity nomenclature code numbers. It is checked that the information about the goods in the relevant columns of the customs cargo declaration match each other. In the implementation of foreign economic relations, that is, in the process of export and import of goods, each commodity is classified in accordance with international code numbers based on the international economic activity based on a system of systematic harmonization of foreign economic activities based on the commodity nomenclature. goods are classified according to the main rules of interpretation of foreign economic activity commodity nomenclature. In order to correctly determine the code of the goods, it is done by knowing all their characteristics.

As mentioned above, customs fees are charged in full on the basis of determining the correct foreign economic activity commodity nomenclature code numbers. Implementation of systematic reforms in the customs system in order to optimize and simplify administrative methods and eliminate bureaucratic obstacles is one of the urgent tasks. Therefore, as a result of the correct determination of the code numbers of the foreign economic activity commodity nomenclature, customs fees are collected in full [1].

Literature analysis on the topic.

Foreign scientists, including Korf D.V, Yakubova E.V, Andreeva E.I, Vorotentseva T.M, N.P.Sorokina, S.A.Vilkova, L.A.Yakovleva, K.A.Alymbekov, O.Y.Svekolnikova and others, among the scientists of our country I.R.Kyrgyzov, A.M. Joraev, N.Kh. Tukhtaboev, M.Yu. Isakov, A.J. Abdurakhmonova and others contributed. They created the principles of identification, classification and certification of goods based on their chemical composition. In particular, recommendations have been made to put into practice the identification of certain export-import products based on the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity with the help of customs expertise. However, the complete classification of perfumery and cosmetic products based on their chemical composition was not provided in these studies. Therefore, the purpose of our research work is to classify goods in the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity based on their chemical composition [2-3].

In particular, Russian scientists, G.A.Antonov, V.G.Versin, N.V. Voitolovsky, M.Y.Goloshubov, N.I.Gusev, A.A.Dechenko, O.V.Kalinina, E.M.Deafness, v.p. Koeco, A.V. Kuleshov, V.M. Larin, V.V. Maksusaev, V.V. Korpilov, V.A. Poliakova, Rudakova, R.P.Sadikova, B.C.Studies have been conducted by Sinavin and other similar scientists [4-8].

Risk management system is used in the customs services of Russia, Turkey, Finland and other countries. Selective customs control based on risk indicators has been implemented since the 1990s as part of the implementation of the

International Convention on the Control of Goods at Borders. Not only goods, but also vehicles began to be considered as objects of customs control.

The harmonized system of description and coding of goods used to form the system of customs tariffs is an important area of international cooperation in the field of customs.

Therefore, like almost all countries in the world, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity has been developed on the basis of a harmonized system of description and coding of goods. Foreign economic activity, maintenance of commodity nomenclature and classification of goods is one of the components of customs work and important tasks assigned to customs authorities. This issue is of particular importance regarding the application of customs management measures to one or another commodity. The customs value of the goods and the customs rates applied to them depend on the correct classification of the goods according to the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity [9-11].

Based on the above, it is important to improve the rules for the classification of goods according to the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity.

Research methodology

Systematic analysis, historicity and logic, analysis and synthesis, and comparative analysis methods were used as research methodology. In the implementation of foreign economic relations, that is, in the process of export and import of goods, each commodity is classified in accordance with international code numbers based on the international economic activity based on a system of systematic harmonization of foreign economic activities based on the commodity nomenclature. goods are classified according to the main rules of interpretation of foreign economic activity commodity nomenclature. In order to correctly determine the code of the goods, it is done by knowing the main characteristics of the goods.

As mentioned above, customs fees are charged in full on the basis of determining the correct foreign economic activity commodity nomenclature code numbers. It is checked that the information about the goods in the relevant columns of the customs cargo declaration match each other. Therefore, as a result of correctly determining the code numbers of the foreign economic activity commodity nomenclature, the customs fees are collected in full.

Analysis and results

According to the data of the State Customs Committee at the end of 2021, in 2021, 9596 (2020: 4,050) expertises were conducted by the goods classification teams of the Central Customs Laboratory and Regional Customs Departments. As a result of the expertises, 3291 (2,771) errors related to the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity were found, and 99.9 billion sums (83.05 billion soums in 2020) were collected as additional customs fees.

In 2021, compared to the same period last year, the number of expertises was 5546, the number of detected errors was 520, and the estimated customs fees were 16.85 billion. 44% in Tashkent city and 2-8% in the rest of the regions, errors in the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity were found [12].

Statistical analyzes for 4 years (2019y, 2020y, 2021y, 2022y) based on the work carried out by the goods classification groups of the Central Customs Laboratory and Regional Customs Departments are as follows (Table 1).

As a result of 9943 (9596 in 2021) expertises carried out by the Commodity Classification teams of the regional customs departments of the State Customs Committee in the reporting period of 2022, 3540 (3,291 in 2021) errors related to the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity were identified, 77, 5 billion sums (99.9 billion in 2021) were estimated as additional customs fees (of which 56.2 billion sums were collected, 7.3 billion sums were collected under control, and 13.9 billion sums were collected due to some reasons (re-export, court decisions, Checkout was disabled due to unavailability of certificate, devalued, etc.

1-table

**In the direction of customs expertise by the Central Customs Laboratory
and regional customs departments
INFORMATION**

	2019	2020	2021	2022
Conducted expertises total number	3794	4050	9596	9943
Foreign economic activity is determined by the commodity nomenclature number of errors	2257	2771	3291	3540
Additional payments calculated as a result of errors identified in the nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity (billion.sum)	45,42	83,05	99,95	77,5

(It was prepared by the author based on the information of the State Customs Committee)

According to the data in Table 1, the number of expertises conducted in 2022 compared to the same period last year increased by 338, the number of detected errors increased by 297, and the estimated customs fees decreased by 22.4 billion sums.

In 2022, the Central Customs Laboratory received 316 (330 in 2021) appeals (298 from regional customs administrations, 11 from legal entities and individuals, 7 from the General Directorate of the Customs Administration of the Customs Service) in 2022. 7 billion sums of additional customs fees were calculated [9].

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In 2022, the following foreign economic commodity Nomenclature code errors were identified as a result of the examination, and the customs examination revealed the correct foreign economic commodity Nomenclature code of the commodity: of these, the external economic commodity nomenclature 35, 39, 48, 59, 60, 72, 73, 83, 84, 85, 87, 90, 92, 94, 95- the most identified errors in their groups. As can be seen from the above data, cases of changing and misrepresenting the code numbers of foreign economic commodity nomenclature of goods associated with non-payment or reduction of customs duties in the entry of goods into the territory of our country are increasing from year to year.

Such cases, in turn, are directly related to the direction of Customs Examination. From 4-year (2019y, 2020y, 2021y 2022y) analytical data, it will be possible to see that foreign economic activity is constantly increasing from year to year due to errors associated with commodity Nomenclature code numbers, cases of customs duty evasion [13-14].

So, the above information shows that from year to year there are cases of incorrect classification of goods and reduced payment of customs duties to the state budget, in order to avoid such negative circumstances, first it is proposed to correctly interpret the rules of classification and establish the implementation of customs examination of certain complex goods.

Conclusions and suggestions

1. In order to improve the knowledge and qualifications of inspectors of the customs post of foreign economic activity according to the Basic Rules for the classification of goods according to the commodity nomenclature of foreign economic activity, in cooperation with professors and teachers of the customs Institute, the" expert advice "is the

organization of the rUK and the official" customs.uz "on the Internet site or in the manner of a" video projector "regularly organize training sessions of the" Master class "in the" on-line " mode every month, at the end of the quarter. We believe that regional training seminars with the participation of experts of the Harmonized System of the World Customs Organization are also aimed at organizing scientific seminars, conferences (conferences, briefings) together with foreign specialists, participants of foreign economic activity.

2. To regularly create and update risk profiles on suspicious goods, in order to clarify that the code of nomenclature of goods of foreign economic activity is correctly classified. External economic activity to activate the work carried out in the field of determining the code of commodity nomenclature and increase the efficiency of group work, establish logical control with the risk management system and warn against the risks associated with the code of commodity nomenclature of future foreign economic activity, create opportunities to avoid shortcomings and errors in the formalization process.

3. In order to improve the knowledge and qualifications of inspectors of customs post of foreign economic activity on the Basic Rules of classification of goods according to commodity nomenclature of foreign economic activity, taking into account the fact that there is no methodological manual in Uzbek on the application of the Basic Rules of classification of goods, territorial customs departments create a methodological manual for inspectors of customs posts.

4. In order to reduce the number of errors in the classification of goods by commodity nomenclature of foreign economic activity, to coordinate the work of employees of the classification of goods in territorial structural formations, to analyze the correct classification of goods formalized through unified electronic information systems of customs authorities.

5. It is advisable to develop mechanisms for improving and classifying the process of identification of goods and detailing in accordance with the nomenclature of foreign economic activity goods and carry out Customs Examination.

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